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Design and analysis of scarf repairs with circular and rounded rectangular repair cutouts

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Ultrafan engine

Multi-core sandwich impact liner

Carbon fibre casing

Introduction

- Composite repair of primary load bearing structure.

Portable waterjet system
for automatic step sanding
operation

Scarfed fuselage surface

- Need for repair strategy for high aspect ratio damages.
- Exploring different repair shapes against benchmarked repair strategies.
- Localized repair for lower down time of aircraft.
- Improvement of damage tolerance
- In service damages come in various shapes and sizes.
- Could not be disassembled in various repair scenarios
- Undamaged high cost composites could not be reused

Background and recent developments

- Damaged structure must be restored back to ultimate design strength [1]
- Impact properties change with scarf angles [2]
- The optimum geometry to repair structure against biaxial loading was studied numerically [3]
- New challenge is to repair primary structures without removing the damaged components from aircraft with minimal grounding time.
- Roll-Royce Ultrafan engine with primary load bearing components like Ti-C fan blades, multi-core composite impact liners and carbon fiber casings to be launched 2025.
- A350 XWB's certification, the team used the full-scale test specimen and fatigue tests to qualify their processes and reach Technology Readiness Level 6 (TRL 6).

GE patent on localized repair

- US Patent Number US 8,371,009 B2 , The patent document states that because engines would operate in a variety of conditions, foreign objects such as large birds, hailstones, ice, sand and rain may undesirably enter the engine and become entrained in the inlet of the engine where they may impact the engine or fan blade.
- The repair process “involves an abradable system having at least one damaged portion, and comprising a sandwich structure and at least one abradable layer, removing the damaged portion of the abradable system to leave a hole, shaping a sandwich structure segment to produce a shaped sandwich structure, infusing a resin into the shaped sandwich structure, curing the shaped sandwich structure, bonding the shaped sandwich structure in the hole in the abradable system, and applying at least one abradable layer to the shaped sandwich structure to produce the containment casing having a repaired integrated abradable system

Design of scarf repair

- Stress distribution along the scarf joint is uniform for a feather edge adherent
- Stress concentration occurs otherwise

If the stiffness and expansion co-efficient of parent and patch are same, a first approximation of average bond line stresses are

$$\tau_{av} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma^\infty \sin 2\alpha$$

$$\sigma_{av} = \sigma^\infty \sin^2 \alpha$$

Where $\sigma^\infty = \frac{P}{wt}$, α - scarf angle, P -applied load

t - thickness of adherent, w – width of the adherent

Design of scarf joints

The adhesive joint strength is

$$\sigma_{\text{joint}} = \frac{2\tau_Y}{K_\tau \sin 2\alpha}$$

The scarf angle required to withstand the ultimate design strength is

$$\alpha_b = \frac{1}{2} \sin^{-1} \frac{2\tau_Y}{K_\tau \sigma_{\text{ULT}}}$$

With $\tau_{\text{max}} \leq \tau_Y$

Normalized strength ratio $K_\tau \sigma_{\text{repair}} / \tau_Y$ versus scarf angle.

Ref: Bonded Joints and Repairs to Composite Airframe Structures by Chun H. Wang Cong N. Duong

The minimum scarf angle for $\epsilon_U = 4000$ micro strain is **~3.85°**

The stress concentration factors could be predicted using FEM with improved accuracy

This is an stress based failure criterion without considering plastic yielding of adhesive.

Determination of design space

Glass fiber reinforced polymer composite: HexPly M21/37%/7581.
 Adhesive: 3M AF 3109-2k

Localized repair of GFRP laminate

(a)

(b)

(c)

Installation of pneumatic routers

Secondary bonding and NDT of bonded patch

Preparation of repair patch; Surface preparation: White Alumina grit blasted followed by acetone degreased

Testing

(a) 3.5 kg steel impactor; (b) Double picture frame

Test setup for 37 J impact

Force versus time response

- Initial response of all three configuration samples were similar.
- Post delamination rounded rectangular samples load carrying capacity is against circular and pristine.
- Circular repairs response is very similar to that of pristine
- There is an inverse relationship between the peak force experienced and the size of the specimen's delamination area.

Energy versus time response

- It can be seen that the energy absorbed by sample post peak impact for rounded rectangular is the least followed by circular repair and pristine.
- Circular repair sample has similar energy absorption trend as that of Pristine sample.
- The area under the curve for each energy versus time response has proportionate delamination size.

Failure analysis

	Pristine laminate, C	Circular repaired laminate, G	Rounded rectangular repaired laminate, I
Delamination area, mm ²	181.63	199.64	970.33

Shyr, T. W., & Pan, Y. H. (2003). Impact resistance and damage characteristics of composite laminates. *Composite structures*, 62(2), 193-203.

Conclusion

- Inverse relationship between peak force and delamination area
- Peak force of circular scarf geometry is lower by 8% while rounded rectangular geometry is lower by 15% against pristine sample.
- Higher stiffness homogeneity leads to better localization of damages
- Direct relationship between energy absorbed and delamination area
- Circular scarf repair results in smaller and more symmetrical damage area
- Force-time and energy-time response of circular repaired specimen resembled closer to that of pristine specimen

References

- [1] C. H. Wang and C. N. Duong, "Introduction and overview," in Bonded Joints and Repairs to Composite Airframe Structures 1st ed., 2016, pp. 3-19.
- [2] H. Hoshi, K. Nakano, and Y. Iwahori, "Study on Repair of CFRP Laminates for Aircraft Structures," in 16th International Conference on Composite Material, Kyoto, Japan, 2007.
- [3] C. H. Wang and A. J. Gunnion, "Optimum shapes of scarf repairs," Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, vol. 40, no. 9, pp. 1407-1418, 2009.